

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HUMAN PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: The article examines the history of artificial intelligence systems, their place in human activity, artificial intelligence technologies and the importance of implementing artificial intelligence systems.

Key words: Information and communication technologies, telecommunications, software, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается история систем искусственного интеллекта, их место в деятельности человека, технологии искусственного интеллекта и важность внедрения систем искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова: Информационно-коммуникационные технологии, телекоммуникации, программное обеспечение, искусственный интеллект..

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt tizimlarining tarixi , insoniyat faoliyatida tutgan o'rni, sun'iy intellektning texnologiyasi va sun'iy intellekt tizimlarini hayotga tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, Telekommunikatsiya, dasturiy ta'minot, sun'iy intellekt..

INTRODUCTION

Usually, when people think of robots, they imagine assistants that can talk like humans and do all the work for them. But this is a relatively broader concept. In fact, the applications on your mobile device: Google Translate, dictionaries, various games, etc., can also be a bright example of artificial intelligence. It's just that their scope of activity is smaller, and they can only help you in a certain direction. That is, you use the appropriate program depending on the type of action you want to perform.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Artificial intelligence is a specific area of computer science that deals with the creation of computer systems with capabilities typically associated with human intelligence: language understanding, learning, reasoning, problem solving, translation, and similar capabilities. Currently, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms and software systems designed to perform various tasks, and it can perform many of the tasks that the human mind can perform.

The 1990s marked a new chapter in the development of artificial intelligence. In 1997, IBM's Deep Blue became the first computer in history to defeat world chess champion Garry Kasparov.

Another striking example of artificial intelligence is the IBM Watson supercomputer, which uses its database to answer questions asked in a specific language. Other achievements of artificial intelligence include applications such as Siri, a mobile assistant that has become a constant companion for many people, and Prisma, a photo editing program. Today, artificial intelligence has become widely popular, covering almost all aspects of our daily lives. For example, residents of Yinchuan, China, do not need bank cards. All processes related to calculations are carried out by artificial intelligence by identifying a human face.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The debate about artificial intelligence has been going on for almost 50 years. Experts still disagree. Some are concerned that their popularity and displacement could lead to increased unemployment. Another group of experts advocates a positive attitude towards artificial intelligence.

Even among billionaires in the IT industry, there are different opinions.

In particular, SpaceX founder Elon Musk is convinced that artificial intelligence will destroy entire civilizations.

Musk believes that "Artificial intelligence is the biggest threat to human civilization. Artificial intelligence will cause huge problems with the workforce. The reason is that robots can do everything better than us. As a result of chasing advanced technologies, companies may not notice the dangers that artificial intelligence brings."

Microsoft CEO Bill Gates also discusses the technology's downsides. "In a few decades, when robots are doing most of the work, AI will become so powerful that it will eventually start to worry us. I agree with Elon Musk on that. But I can't understand why this issue doesn't worry others," Gates said.

It is not surprising that by "others" Gates meant Facebook owner Mark Zuckerberg. Because Mark expressed his positive attitude towards artificial intelligence: "New technologies can always be created for good or evil. We will see positive results from the widespread use of artificial intelligence in the next five to 10 years," he countered Elon Musk's opinion.

Today, some countries use robot nurses, driverless cars, and drones for delivery. Even some police duties are performed by special robots. Scientists are trying to make their appearance as similar to humans as possible.

In addition, artificial intelligence has become a permanent assistant to journalists. For example, robots "working" at the Associated Press write financial reports. The use of artificial intelligence has allowed the number of quarterly news items in this publication to increase from 300 to 4,400.

According to insurance company Swiss Re, 4.7 million people could be out of work by 2020. It was also said that unemployment could threaten treasurers, postal workers, accountants and office workers. Artificial intelligence will easily cope with this task.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In addition to the above, one of the obstacles to the popularization of artificial intelligence is the fact that most consumers do not trust robots. Of course, it will take some time for people to accept the services of driverless cars and planes. However, for the younger generation, which grows up surrounded by modern technology, it is the opposite, and this process does not bother them so much.

Despite all the objections and criticism, artificial intelligence continues to develop and help people. Its importance is growing, especially in medicine. Now robots are able to perform even relatively complex surgeries. The unique cooperation of robot doctors with medical personnel has significantly increased efficiency.

Medtronis, in collaboration with IBM, is developing a special program for patients with diabetes. This software will be able to detect an emergency drop in blood sugar levels within 3 hours. For this purpose, medical records of 600 anonymous patients with this disease were studied. This means that now people will have the opportunity to regularly monitor their health using special applications on mobile devices.

As you can see, the role of artificial intelligence in our lives is growing every day. The debate about whether they are a triumph or a defeat for humanity will continue for a long time. The most important thing, according to science fiction writer Isaac Asimov, is that the motto when creating robots should be to avoid causing harm to people.

8 Facts About Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence is a specific field of computer science that deals with the creation of computer systems with capabilities typically associated with human intelligence: language understanding, learning, reasoning, problem solving, translation, and similar capabilities.

While scientists are enthusiastic about experimenting with artificial intelligence (AI), many people view the phenomenon with trepidation. Even Tesla CEO Elon Musk has called it a “grave threat” to humanity and a potential source of war and unemployment.

Let's take a look at 8 interesting facts about artificial intelligence.

Fact 1. The artificial intelligence service is free and limited in time.

Fact 2. It can adapt to failures. American scientists conducted an experiment with a robot equipped with artificial intelligence. They found that the device continued to work even in the event of serious injuries. During the experiment, the “injured” robot was able to adapt to at least six different injuries, including the complete loss of two lower limbs, and the robot’s “arm” was able to adapt to at least 14 types of injuries, including the failure of two of its motors.

Fact 3: Artificial intelligence inherits the beliefs and stereotypes of its creators. Artificial brains draw conclusions based on the information they initially receive, so they are subject to racial and gender biases. Studies have shown that some computer facial recognition systems confuse the gender of black women 35% of the time and only 0.8% of white men. This is because the photos in the databases that artificial intelligence works with are 75% male, 80% of whom are white.

Fact 4: Artificial intelligence can answer questions.

The most powerful text generator to date, based on OpenAI's GPT-2 AI, can write entire paragraphs without making mistakes. At the same time, the system will correctly answer questions if they relate to general knowledge.

Fact 5. Artificial intelligence can learn everything that humans can do. Researchers hope that by 2060, artificial intelligence will be able to independently perform almost all human tasks. For example, scientists at Oxford University, in collaboration with Google's DeepMind AI division, taught a system to read lips better than humans. The Watch, Attend and Spell program detects the difference between words with similar lip movements and analyzes up to 50% of silent speech. The system was trained by watching BBC news programs. After learning 118,000 sentences from videos, watch, participate, and spell more than 17,500 words.

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Fact 6. Robots with artificial intelligence are already working as announcers, flying into space, patrolling ships and playing football.

A robot newsreader reads the news at China's state news agency Xinhua. It was created based on a real prototype by Zhang Wanwei. The robot can not only read news texts, but also learn from its human counterparts by imitating their facial expressions and speech patterns.

The CIMON 2 robot communicates with astronauts on the ISS: it uses IBM's Watson system as its artificial intelligence. An update using the Watson Tone Analyzer service allows CIMON 2 to understand and respond to human emotions. The CIMON project was developed by the German Aerospace Center in cooperation with Airbus and IBM.

Norwegian oil company Aker BP uses a robot dog named Spot (developed by Boston Dynamics) to guard one of its ships. Modern robots can even play football: such models were created by an artificial intelligence group at the Free University of Berlin.

Fact 7: Artificial intelligence can help in the fight against coronavirus. Around the world, AI-based systems are helping to track infected people, collect information about the virus, and search for a vaccine. For example, the Israeli company Vocalis Health, in collaboration with the Israeli government, has developed a technology for detecting COVID-19 based on voice spectrum analysis. In addition, AI-powered robots are being used to patrol public places (Singapore). Using Megvii ReID technology, a system has been developed in China that can identify people with high temperatures in a crowd.

Fact 8. Artificial intelligence is designed to save the planet and provide people with food.

NatureServe, a nonprofit that focuses on biodiversity conservation in the U.S., Canada, and Latin America, has partnered with data analytics company SAS on a global initiative called Data for Good. Artificial intelligence is being used to collect data on plant and animal species, their locations, and population concentrations.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) also recognizes the benefits of artificial intelligence, saying that “intelligence” will allow farmers to plan their work more effectively, taking into account information about weather conditions, pests, soil moisture and other important indicators.

CONCLUSION

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the above-listed areas of application of artificial intelligence are important areas of human activity today. Artificial intelligence is widely used not only in the areas listed, but also in other areas and directions. In conclusion, it should be noted that artificial intelligence is becoming increasingly popular in industry, science and professional human activity, acquiring increasing importance in the development of all systems of our society.

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